

CURE MONITORING OF THICK CFRP LAMINATE BY OPTICAL-FIBER-BASED DISTRIBUTED SENSOR

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1 Introduction

Advanced composite structures, which have high specific strength and stiffness, have been used extensively in many industrial fields. One of the main applications is aircraft, where they are applied to primary structures like main wings and used under harsh environments. Therefore, quality certification of these composite structures, which are very dependent on their curing process, has been a key issue on the reliable products [1-3]. And they usually have thick laminate structure to get enough toughness and have temperature distribution inside during cure process, which causes unexpected strain development and residual distortion after curing. Accordingly, measurement and comprehension in curing process of these thick composite structures are necessary for reliability of products.

To monitor the several variables during of curing materials, some cure-monitoring techniques exist, such as differential scanning calorimetry [4], dielectrometry [5], and point type optical fiber sensors including extrinsic Fabry-Perot type sensors [6,7], Raman spectroscopy [8], and fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors [9-11]. Among these techniques, optical fiber sensors are very useful for monitoring of strain and temperature inside during cure process. Since they are light weight and small and rarely affect the mechanical properties of the materials in which they are embedded. However, almost of the optical fiber sensors can monitor only at a few or limited number of measuring points. They can not measure strain distribution in large structure. Overcoming this problem, distributed optical fiber sensors, which can measure the strain or temperature distribution along an optical fibre, were developed recently [12]. They are now considered as

an effective sensing system to monitor the curing large composite structures [13].

In this study, the authors applied the optical-fiber-based distributed sensor to cure monitoring of thick composite structure which has temperature distribution in the thickness direction. The experimental results were verified by FEM analysis with elastic and visco-elastic cure model to reveal the effect of the temperature distribution on the complicated strain history in cure process.

2 Measurement Principles

The author used the pulse-pre-pump Brillouin optical time domain analysis (PPP-BOTDA) as the distributed optical fiber based sensor. This technique can measure the temperature and strain changes along optical fiber with frequency shift of the Brillouin backscattering light at each point. The measured shifts, which is denoted by $\Delta\nu_B$, is a function of temperature and strain applied at the point and expressed by the following equation:

$$\Delta\nu_B = C_1\Delta\varepsilon + C_2\Delta T \quad (1)$$

In the equation, $\Delta\varepsilon$ and ΔT are changes of applied strain and temperature respectively. C_1 and C_2 are coefficients of each strain and temperature effect. These two values had been determined by preliminary experiments, where the only strain or temperature change was applied. Upon this equation, the measuring frequency shift includes both strain and temperature effect in curing process, and hence thermocouples are embedded together for temperature effect compensation. The strain values are calculated by the following equation:

$$\Delta\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta v_B - C_2 \Delta T}{C_1} \quad (2)$$

3 Strain distribution in cure shrinkage process

3.1 Experimental setup

Material of the specimen was T800S/3900-2B (Toray Industries, Inc.). Stacking configuration was $[90_{80}]$. Fig. 1 is the illustration of a carbon/epoxy specimen indicating location of the embedded optical fiber sensor and the thermocouples. The embedded sensor were located between 8-9, 24-25, 40-41, 56-57 and 72-73 (numbered from bottom) plies in the specimen. The optical fiber is located in the center of specimen, whose embedded direction is perpendicular to carbon fibers in plies. The three thermocouples were embedded respectively in the same plies for compensation. The specimen with the embedded sensor was cured in an autoclave. No pressure was applied to measure the cure shrinkage strain clearly. The specimen was heated with only a bottom heating plate. The temperature history recommended for this material is (1) rising by around 2 °C/min from room temperature to 180 °C, (2) holding at 180 °C for 2hours (epoxy curing) (3)

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of specimen with embedded optical fiber sensors and thermocouples.

cooling down to room temperature. The sensors measured strain and temperature with respect to each 2 min during cure.

3.2 Experimental result

Fig. 2 shows the temperature histories measured by the thermocouples embedded at center part in each plies. These are located at almost same position in plane. The each ply distributed in the thickness direction has clearly different temperature history. And the lower part of specimen had higher temperature than the upper part for all over the cure process. The gap between holding temperature of 8-9 plies and 72-73 plies was even 40 °C. The heating method by only the bottom heating plate caused that temperature distribution in the specimen. Such temperature distribution can occur in thick composite structures regardless of heating method like hot air and so on.

Using the histories for the temperature compensation of measured results by PPP-BOTDA, the strain history in each ply was calculated. Since the each measuring points distributed in the same ply had the almost same strain (and temperature) history, Fig. 3 shows the calculated strain histories at the center points of each ply distributed in the thickness direction. In this graph, the each ply distributed in the thickness direction has clearly different strain history especially in (2) epoxy curing step and (3) cooling down step. During step (1) when the temperature rose and degree of cure value was lower, the epoxy in the specimen has very low viscosity

Fig. 2. Temperature history in thickness direction.

and the developed stress can get relaxed within a fraction of a second. On another front, the epoxy had visco-elastic or elastic behavior and the temperature distribution might develop residual strain and stress distribution after holding. In this study, the author focused the important and rarely investigated strain distribution developed in (2) epoxy curing step. The strain distribution with applied pressure in (3) cooling down step was investigated in the latter session in this paper.

The effect of temperature distribution to strain history can be related to two important parameters, beginning time of cure shrinkage and total amount of shrinkage strain during epoxy curing. The beginning times of cure shrinkage were different in each ply. The lower part of the specimen started to

sharply shrink earlier than the upper part due to the temperature distribution in the thickness direction. When the lower part started to shrink sharply, the upper part saw to shrink gradually getting affected by the shrinkage of the lower part. Next, to evaluate total amount of shrinkage strain during epoxy curing (80 min to 250 min), they in each ply were calculated from Fig. 3. And Fig. 4 shows the result. The total amount of strain ranged from 4200 μm to 5500 μm . The upper part had the larger shrinkage strain than lower part. The value of 4200 μm in 8-9 plies was the almost same as that had been obtained by the previous measurement with a thin specimen which had uniform temperature filed. And when the lower parts started to shrink sharply by their own cure shrinkage phenomena, the upper parts had low viscosity. Accordingly, the shrinkage of the lower parts could affect the total shrinkage of the upper part as visco-elastic behavior.

Fig. 3. Strain history in thickness direction.

Fig. 4. Total shrinkage strain in thickness direction

3.4 Analysis model

Two FEM analysis with different cure models were executed with fortran 90 code. One was “Elastic cure model” which included a degree of cure sub-model, a cure shrinkage sub-model and a cure hardening instantaneously linear elastic (CHILE) model. Another was “Visco-elastic cure model” which included the degree of cure sub-model (same as the Elastic cure model), cure shrinkage sub-model (same as the Elastic cure model) and the visco-elastic cure model [14]. The details of each model were written latter. Fig. 5 shows the model size of the two analyses. Corresponding to the temperature histories of the experiment, each model had five different temperature historys parts and upper parts had higher holding temperature than lower parts. The applied temperature history as input were (1) rising in 80min from room temperature to the holding temperature of each part (160, 170, 180, 190, 200°C) and (2) holding for 2hours. Fig. 6 shows the input temperature historys of each parts.

Model 1 (elastic cure model)

The following equation expressed the degree of cure sub-model:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2\alpha) \cdot (1 - \alpha) \cdot (0.47 - \alpha) \quad \alpha \leq 0.3 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_3 \cdot (1 - \alpha) \quad 0.3 < \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$k_1 = A_1 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{dE_1}{RT}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$k_2 = A_2 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{dE_2}{RT}\right) \quad (6)$$

$$k_3 = A_3 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{dE_3}{RT}\right) \quad (7)$$

In this equation, α and t were degree of cure of epoxy and time. The coefficients k_i , A_i and E_i ($i=1\sim3$) were the model parameters had been decided by the experiment. R and T were gas constant and temperature. The following equation expressed the cure shrinkage sub-model:

$$\varepsilon_{sh} = 0.0 \quad (\alpha < \alpha_{c1}) \quad (8)$$

$$\varepsilon_{sh} = \varepsilon_t \cdot \alpha_s \quad (\alpha_{c1} \leq \alpha \leq \alpha_{c2}) \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha_s = \frac{\alpha - \alpha_{c1}}{\alpha_{c2} - \alpha_{c1}} \quad (10)$$

ε_{sh} and ε_t were cure shrinkage strain and the total cure shrinkage strain. α_s , α_{c1} and α_{c2} were degree of cure to calculate cure shrinkage, one when resin shrinkage begins and one when resin shrinkage stops. The following equation expressed the CHILE model:

$$E(\alpha, \xi) = E_0 + (E_c - E_0) \cdot \alpha \quad (11)$$

$$v = 0.3 \quad (10)$$

E , E_0 and E_c were composite elastic modulus, composite elastic modulus at very low degree of cure and composite elastic modulus at $\alpha=1.0$. v was composite Poisson's ratio.

Model 2 (visco-elastic cure model)

The following equation expressed the visco-elastic cure model:

$$E(\alpha, \xi) = E_c \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\xi}{\tau(\alpha)}\right) \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta\xi = \frac{\Delta t}{a_T(\alpha, T)} \quad (14)$$

$$\tau(\alpha) = \tau_0 \cdot 10^{f(\alpha) - (\alpha - 0.98)(9.9 - \log \tau_0)} \quad (15)$$

$$f(\alpha) = 0.0536 + 0.0615\alpha + 0.9227 \cdot \alpha^2 \quad (16)$$

ξ and t were reduced time and stress relaxation time. α_T and τ_0 were shift factor for time-temperature superposition and peak relaxation time. The all values used in these models were summarized in Table. 1

3.3 Analysis result

Fig. 7 shows the degree of cure histories calculated with the degree of cure sub-model (equation (3)-(7)). The five different temperature histories parts had different degree of cure histories. And the degree of cure in the higher temperature parts increased earlier than the lower temperature parts.

Fig. 8 and 9 show the calculated strain histories with elastic cure model and visco-elastic cure model. The both of the results expressed suddenly cure shrinkage strain drop. With the elastic cure model, the strain was constant after epoxy curing. On the other hand, the strain distribution after curing was obtained with visco-elastic model.

Fig. 10 and 11 show the total shrinkage strain value distributed in thickness direction with elastic cure model and visco-elastic cure model. The black line in these graph expressed the experimental result. The analytical result with elastic cure model was different from the experimental result. The one with visco-elastic cure model had similar value and trend that the total shrinkage increased as a function of ply number.

From these analytical results, visco-elastic behavior can bring total shrinkage strain distribution during epoxy curing step when temperature and degree of cure distribution exist in the thickness direction.

Table. 1. Material properties used in the simulation

A_1	0.35×10^8 /sec	ε_t	4.0×10^3 $\mu\epsilon$
A_2	-0.34×10^8 /sec	α_{c1}	0.6
A_3	0.33×10^5 /sec	α_{c2}	1.0
dE_1	8.07×10^4 J/mol	E_0	0.08 GPa
dE_2	7.78×10^4 J/mol	E_c	8.0 GPa
dE_3	5.66×10^4 J/mol	v	0.3
R	8.31 J/mol/K	τ_0	7.94×10^9 min

Fig. 5. Analytical model and temperature distribution in thickness direction in FEM

Fig. 8. Strain history at measuring points distributed in thickness direction.

Fig. 6. Temperature history at measuring points distributed in thickness direction.

Fig. 9. Strain history at measuring points distributed in thickness direction.

Fig. 7. Degree of cure history at measuring points distributed in thickness direction.

Fig. 10. Total shrinkage strain distributed in thickness direction

Fig. 11. Total shrinkage strain in thickness direction

4 Strain distribution in cooling down process

4.1 Experimental setup

Material of the specimen was T800S/3900-2B (Toray Industries, Inc.). Stacking configuration was $[90_{80}]$. Fig. 12 is the illustration of a carbon/epoxy specimen indicating location of the embedded optical fiber sensor and the thermocouples. The embedded sensors were located between each 10-11, 21-22, 50-51, and 70-71 (numbered from bottom) plies in the specimen. The optical fiber is located in the center of specimen, whose embedded direction is perpendicular to carbon fibers in plies. The three thermocouples were embedded respectively in the same plies for compensation. The specimen with the embedded sensor was cured in an autoclave. The pressure in the autoclave was kept at 0.5MPa. The specimen was heated with only a bottom heating plate. Before a cooling step, to relieve the effect of pressure and boundary condition to strain development in cooling step, the applied pressure had been gradually decreased to atmospheric pressure during holding step.

4.2 Experimental result

Fig. 13 shows the temperature histories measured by the thermocouples embedded at center part in each plies. These are located at almost same position in plane. The each ply distributed in the thickness direction has clearly different temperature history. (In this session, the author focused the temperature

and strain after about 900 min.) And the lower part of specimen had higher temperature than the upper part for all over the cure process. The gap between holding temperature of 10-11 plies and 70-71 plies was even 20 °C. (The difference of applied pressure could produce the smaller gap between the holding temperatures compared with the previous experiment in session 3.)

Using the histories for the temperature compensation of measured results by PPP-BOTDA, the strain history in each ply was calculated. Fig. 14 shows the calculated strain histories at the center points of each ply distributed in the thickness direction. In this graph, the each ply distributed in the thickness direction has clearly different strain history.

Total amount of shrinkage strain in cooling step and CTE (coefficient of temperature expansion) were calculated by Fig 14. Fig. 15 and 16 show the total strain and CTE in each plies. The holding temperature gap brought the strain and CTE distribution.

Next, to use for calculating CTE in an analysis to evaluate these experimental result, the volume fraction of cured specimen was measured by microscope observation. Fig. 17 shows one example of the measured cross sectional views. The lighter

Fig. 12. Schematic diagram of specimen with embedded optical fiber sensors and thermocouples.

part corresponded to carbon fibers and darker one corresponded to epoxy matrix. Fig. 18 shows the calculated V_f distribution. The V_f was not uniform in the specimen. The values increased as a function of ply number from 0 ply to 60 ply. The values near the upper and the bottom surface were lower. The vacuuming from both surfaces for applying pressure had epoxy flow to the both surfaces and the vacuuming from the bottom surface might be stronger.

Fig. 15. Shrinkage strain distribution in thickness direction.

Fig. 13. Temperature history at measuring points distributed in thickness direction.

Fig. 16. CTE distribution in thickness direction.

Fig. 14. Total shrinkage strain in thickness direction

Fig. 17. Cross sectional view of cured specimen.

Fig. 18. Volume fraction distribution in thickness direction calculated by cross sectional view.

4.3 Analysis model

FEM analysis calculating strain distribution during cooling step was executed with 3D elastic cure model by ABAQUS. To evaluate the effect of temperature and V_f distribution, three different analysis were executed.

- (i) The temperature change was different in thickness direction (Fig. 13) and the V_f was uniform.
- (ii) The temperature change was uniform and the V_f was different in thickness direction (Fig. 18).
- (iii) Both of the temperature change and V_f were different in thickness direction.

The following equation expressed the CTE model including V_f [15]:

$$\alpha_1 = \alpha^m + \frac{V_f}{R} \{ E_1^f (\alpha_1^f - \alpha^m) [E^m (1 - v_{23}^f - 2v^m v_{12}^f)(1 - V_f) + E_2^f (1 + v^m) + E_2^f (1 + v^m)(1 - 2v^m)V_f] + 2E^m E_2^f (\alpha_2^f - \alpha^m)(v_{12}^f - v^m)(1 - V_f) \} \quad (17)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \alpha^m + \frac{V_f}{R} \{ E_1^f (\alpha_1^f - \alpha^m)(1 - V_f) [E^m (2v_{12}^f + v^m v_{23}^f - v^m) - E_2^f v^m (1 + v^m)] + 2E_2^f (\alpha_2^f - \alpha^m) [E^m (1 - v^m v_{12}^f)(1 - V_f) + E_1^f (1 - v^{m2})V_f] \} \quad (18)$$

$$R = E^{m2} (1 - v_{23}^f - 2v_{12}^f v_{12}^f)(1 - V_f)^2 + E^m (1 - V_f) \{ E_1^f (1 - v_{23}^f - 4v^m v_{12}^f)V_f + E_2^f [1 + v^m + (1 - v^m)V_f] \} + E_1^f E_2^f (1 + v^m) [1 + (1 - 2v^m)V_f] V_f \quad (19)$$

In this equation, the upper index (f, m) expressed the value of fiber and matrix respectively. The all values used in these models were summarized in Table. 2

4.4 Analysis result

Fig. 18 and 19 show the calculated shrinkage strain and CTE distribution in the thickness direction. The red, blue and black lines corresponded to the results of model (i), (ii) and (iii). The marked points expressed the experimental results.

In Fig. 18, all three analytical results express the strain increase as a function of ply number. The result with model (iii) accorded well to the experimental result.

In Fig. 19, the result with model (ii) and (iii) had similar CTE distribution and accorded to the experimental CTE result. From these results, the analysis including the both effect of temperature and V_f distribution could obtain the strain and CTE distribution in cooling step.

Fig. 19. Analysis model for FEM.

Table. 2. Material properties used in the simulation

E_1^f	296.0 GPa	α_1^f	$-3.06 \times 10^{-6} /K$
E_2^f	13.8 GPa	α_2^f	$6.94 \times 10^{-6} /K$
G_{12}^f	9.0 GPa	E^m	3.24 GPa
G_{23}^f	5.8 GPa	G^m	1.19 GPa
v_{12}^f	0.20	v^m	0.36
v_{23}^f	0.25	α^m	$62.0 \times 10^{-6} /K$

Fig. 18. Shrinkage strain distribution in thickness

Fig. 19. CTE distribution in thickness direction.

5. Conclusion

In this study, the authors applied the optical-fiber-based distributed sensor to cure monitoring of thick composite structure which had temperature distribution in the thickness direction.

The cure shrinkage strain distribution in epoxy curing step was evaluated by the experiment and 2D FEM analysis with elastic and visco-elastic cure models. The lower part of the specimen started to sharply shrink earlier than the upper part due to the temperature distribution in the thickness direction. The upper part had the larger shrinkage strain from lower part. When the lower parts started to shrink sharply by their own cure shrinkage phenomena, the

upper parts had low viscosity. Accordingly, the shrinkage of the lower parts could affect the total shrinkage of the upper part as visco-elastic behavior. The analytical result with elastic cure model was different from the experimental result. The one with visco-elastic cure model had similar value and trend that the total shrinkage increased as a function of ply number.

Next, the thermal shrinkage strain distribution in cooling step was evaluated by the experiment and 3D FEM analysis with elastic cure models. The each ply distributed in the thickness direction had clearly different strain history. And the holding temperature gap brought the strain and CTE distribution. The analysis including the both effect of temperature and V_f distribution could obtain the strain and CTE distribution in cooling step.

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